

ISic1170

I.Sicily inscription 1170

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Text of IGTermini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644945

EDCS 70900816

Bibliography

Brugnone, A. 1974. Iscrizione greche del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos*. 20: 218-264. At 9

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1971. Tre epitafi inediti. *Kokalos*. 17: 184-186. At 185 no.1 tav.55.1

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1170. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4351691>